

(Re)constructing a “Disappeared” Institution: Digital Memory of the Museum of Ethnology of Porto through its Documentary Archive

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Digitisation, as a safeguarding strategy for archives at risk, contributes to the digital preservation of archival material, notably through its structuring, standardisation, and preparation for integration into digital environments. It becomes particularly challenging when it involves the public dissemination of documentation from materially disappeared institutions – contexts in which historical understanding and institutional memory depend exclusively on the surviving archival record. This is the case of the Museum of Ethnology of Porto (MEP, 1945–1994), a materially “disappeared” institution whose scientific, administrative, and museological history persists solely through its inactive archive, currently preserved at Palace of Vilar de Allen (Porto, Portugal), under the responsibility of Património Cultural, I.P. (PCIP) – the Portuguese public entity responsible for the management, safeguarding, and valorisation of cultural heritage – ensuring its custody and having been responsible, until December 2023, for the management of Palace of São João Novo (Porto), the former and only known headquarters of the museum.

In this project, “(re)construction” refers exclusively to the restitution of the institutional memory of the MEP based on the documentary evidence contained in its archive, without implying any attempt at physical or museographic reconstruction of the institution. In this context, “institutional memory” is understood as the reconstruction of institutional functioning from the surviving documentation, rather than as tacit knowledge held by an active organisation.

This demonstration presents the methodological, archival, and digital architecture developed to prepare the MEP archive for public access through *arquiv@* – the online archive of PCIP, which enables the management, organisation, and dissemination of documentary archives under its custody. Although *arquiv@* is a pre-existing platform – not developed within the scope of this project – the contribution presented here focuses on processes of organisation, description, digitisation, documentary structuring, and the development of user-support materials that make the MEP archive accessible, intelligible, and navigable within this institutional environment, addressing different user profiles – including researchers, heritage professionals, and the general public.

The proposal is structured into five interconnected components:

1. Archival structuring: reconstructing institutional logic from the archive

This component presents the process of analysing, organising, and structuring the historical archive of the MEP, including the definition of archival hierarchy (collection, sections, series, process, and document). Diagrams, hierarchical trees, and explanatory schemata illustrate how dispersed documentation was transformed into a coherent system. Its relevance lies in the fact that the MEP has materially disappeared, rendering the archive the sole source for understanding its administrative, scientific, and museological functioning. The demonstration shows how archival organisation enables the

(re)construction of institutional logic from the surviving documentation. It is also acknowledged that this process involves interpretative decisions, particularly in contexts where the original order has been partially lost, requiring the explicit identification of gaps, uncertainties, and reconstructed relationships based on the available evidence.

2. Digitisation and technical dossier: safeguarding and methodological rigour

This component demonstrates the technical digitisation workflow applied to the archive: cleaning, physical preparation, digital capture, quality control, file normalisation, naming conventions, and digital storage. It also presents the technical dossier produced within the project, which graphically represents all stages of the process, including specific cases, metadata models, storage schemas, documentary matrix design, and preparation workflows for future integration into *arquiv@*. The aim is to demonstrate technical rigour, methodological transparency, and consistent documentation – essential for safeguarding a vulnerable archive. This process integrates concerns related to digital preservation, particularly in terms of standardisation, organisation, and preparation for integration into digital environments.

3. Descriptive standardisation and metadata: making the archive intelligible and searchable

This section presents the metadata model developed for the MEP archive, aligned with international standards such as ISAD(G), ISAAR-CPF, and PREMIS. Examples include descriptive fields, contextual notes, relationships between producing entities and documentary series, as well as reconstructed documentary trajectories. Standardised description is demonstrated as a fundamental tool for recovering context, ensuring intelligibility, and enabling future public searchability within *arquiv@*. By aligning with established standards, the model contributes to interoperability and the potential reuse of information in broader digital contexts.

4. User mediation and access pathways in *arquiv@*: guiding discovery and navigation

As the archive will be made available through *arquiv@*, this component presents the materials developed to support user access and navigation: user manuals, explanations of platform functionalities, navigation pathways to locate the MEP archive, and conceptual mockups. The aim is to demonstrate how documentary mediation – user-centred in its approach – ensures the intelligibility of the digital archive, promoting autonomy and clarity in public access. These strategies consider different user profiles – including researchers, heritage professionals, and the general public – and are guided by principles of usability and accessibility.

5. Visualisations and digital narrative: evidencing institutional memory through the archive

This component presents visualisations derived from the documentary structure itself: classification trees, relationship maps between series and producing entities, diagrams of administrative and scientific structures, flows of documentary production and circulation, and the final digital matrix. These visualisations make it possible to understand the organisation and functioning of the MEP exclusively through its archive. The demonstration shows how the visual representation of documentary relationships constitutes an evidence-based digital narrative, rendering the memory of a materially disappeared institution intelligible. Rather than proposing a single narrative, these visualisations allow for multiple readings of the archive, highlighting the complexity and interpretative possibilities of the documentary record.

The demonstration highlights how the articulation between archival organisation, technical digitisation processes, and digital mediation can transform a documentary archive into an accessible, navigable, and comprehensible resource. It also acknowledges that the archive documents practices and processes associated with ethnographic collections, which may raise ethical and historical questions to be considered in future developments, particularly in relation to mediation and access. The case of the MEP may serve as a basis for future approaches to digital preservation in archives of materially disappeared institutions or archives at risk, offering a replicable and adaptable methodological model for other contexts.

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References

International Council on Archives. (2000). ISAD(G): General International Standard Archival Description (2nd ed.). ICA.

International Council on Archives. (2004). ISAAR(CPF): International Standard Archival Authority Record for Corporate Bodies, Persons and Families (2nd ed.). ICA.

Património Cultural, I.P. (n.d.). arquiv@: Arquivo online do Património Cultural, I.P. <https://arquivo.patrimoniocultural.gov.pt/>

PREMIS Editorial Committee. (2015). PREMIS data dictionary for preservation metadata (Version 3.0). Library of Congress. <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v3/premis-3-0-final.pdf>